

1 **The range of Xist transcriptional targets in non-small cell lung cancer: BOK.**

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6 We discovered aberrant activation of Xist in cancer, the non-coding RNA that silences duplicate X
7 chromosomes in females to execute dosage compensation, by studying whole transcription in
8 p53-sufficient and p53-deficient cancer cells (1). We next described high levels of Xist expression that
9 could be triggered by mutation or loss of either of two major tumor suppressors, p53 or Rb (1, 2). We
10 demonstrated a function for Xist in activation and repression of solid tumor gene expression, in humans
11 with breast cancer, driven by p53 loss, and demonstrated a role for the expression of these Xist-modulated
12 genes in subtype selection (instruction of tumor lineage) in breast cancer (3, 4). We also described the
13 existence of Xist ribonucleic protein (Xist RNP) complexes that putatively functioned to dynamically control
14 gene expression in transformed cells (5).

15 We describe here Xist control of transcriptional targets in the lung during transformation (6-9). We
16 demonstrate control of *BOK* gene expression by Xist and a role for this gene expression control in subtype
17 selection in non-small cell lung cancer. Xist activation is likely a widespread and relatively common
18 biological phenomena during solid tumor development and disease progression driven by loss of tumor
19 suppressor (p53/Rb) function. Xist influences subtype selection in non-small cell lung cancer by
20 modulating expression of a wide range of transcriptional targets.
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Results

Here we used cells engineered to contain an Xist transgene, Xist-positive (Xist+) human embryonic stem cell clones, and epithelial cells of the lung that exhibit Xist activation following genetic depletion of p53 (6-8) to demonstrate Xist functions in control of gene expression across the transcriptome and in tumor lineage specification (subtype selection) in lung cancer (9).

Figure 1: Expression of BOK defines the (adeno/squamous) subtype in non-small cell lung cancer.

GSE74706

n=10 adenocarcinoma

n=8 squamous cell carcinoma

Probe ID	<i>p</i> -value	<i>t</i>	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	% DE
A_23_P253029	5.13E-03	3.1632621	-2.29337	1.34	BOK	1657/34183	95.2

In patients with non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC), expression of endothelial cell adhesion molecule *BOK* defined the subtype (Figure 1). We discovered subtype-biased expression of *BOK* by measuring and comparing total transcription between adeno and squamous subtypes of the most prevalent solid tumor type affecting humans, NSCLC.

Figure 2: In Xist+ human embryonic stem cell clones, the BOK gene is differentially expressed.

GSE87231

n=2 Xist- human embryonic stem cell (hES) clones

n=2 Xist+ hES clones

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
666	2.56E-05	0.18	4.2092634	0.75839689	649.22	BOK	569/17710	96.8

Xist expression in human embryonic stem cells was associated with differential expression of *BOK* at the clonal level when studying ES cell gene expression transcriptome-wide (Figure 2). In mice, Xist expression is activated following zygote genome activation, while in humans the start of Xist expression is observed between embryonic 4- and 8-cell stage and continues into pre-implantation development in the morula and blastula (10).

Figure 3: Transgenic insertion of a gene encoding Xist in human cells results in modulation of BOK gene expression.

GSE68109

n=1 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line; vector control (5 day DOX induction)

n=2 HT1080 fibrosarcoma cell line with 1p Xist integration (5 day DOX induction)

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
666	6.74E-01	0.683	4.20E-01	0.2868958	463.79	BOK	3535/18311	80.7

1 In human cells engineered to contain an Xist transgene, forced Xist expression resulted in
2 significant repression of BOK (Figure 3).

3 **Discussion**

4 We provided evidence here describing control of expression of the BOK gene by the non-coding
5 RNA Xist and a role for Xist-driven gene expression control in lineage determination at the clonal level
6 during solid tumorigenesis in humans with non-small cell lung cancer. Like in humans with breast cancer,
7 Xist activation that occurs very early is important for subtype selection and imparts a lasting influence on
8 tumor gene expression at clinical presentation. We are currently studying the molecular mechanisms
9 governing transcriptional induction of Xist; repair of the DNA during replication and damage are candidate
10 pathways that regulate Xist activation (11-13).
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Methods

We used datasets GSE68109, GSE87231, GSE272045 and GSE74706 and for this quantitative differential gene expression study of Xist expression in the primary tumors of humans with non-small cell lung cancer, of the adeno and squamous types.

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